

D4.1 WATERLINE website

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Project
WATERLINE

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The WATERLINE project website (waterline-project.eu) has been established to provide an effective means for public dissemination and communications among the consortium members. The website introduces the background of WATERLINE, consortium members, project news, ongoing activities, and contact information. It will also provide the related data, codes and application developed within the project, as well as publications including journal articles, and presentations, allowing the public free access to the knowledge and outcomes from the project.

Contents

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	3
1. WATERLINE website structure	6
2. WATERLINE website components.....	7
2.1 Header.....	7
2.2 Footer	7
2.3 Project introduction.....	7
2.4 Project partners	12
2.5 Project News & Events	14
2.6 Project outcomes.....	15
2.7 Related projects.....	16
2.8 Contact.....	17
2.9 Visitor statistics.....	18

D4.1 WATERLINE website

1. WATERLINE website structure

The domain “waterline-project.eu” has been secured for the WATERLINE project and used for the website. The target audience of the website includes learners and educators at higher education institutes, user communities, digital technology businesses, water utilities, and government policy makers. It is expected to attract at least 7000 visits during the project.

The WATERLINE website includes the following sections to present the project methodology, share research updates, and disseminate outcomes to the public. The information is organised into five main sections as shown in Table 1.

The Home section introduces the methodology, work packages, and consortium members. The News & Events section provides the updates related to the project, including the latest news, upcoming and past events, and newsletter. The Outcomes section will allow the public to access the outputs from WATERLINE, including Deliverable reports, scientific publications, presentations, and other materials such as codes and videos produced in the project.

Table 1 Structure of WATERLINE website

Main section	Sub section
Home	Aim Methodology Work packages Partners
News & Events	News Events Newsletter
Outcomes	Deliverables Publications Presentations Downloads
Related projects	NA
Contact	NA

2. WATERLINE website components

2.1 Header

Figure 1 shows the WATERLINE header. It displays the project logo, “WATERLINE”, followed by a drop-down menu that users can easily use to navigate different sections of the website. It also provides the links to WATERLINE social media accounts.

Figure 1 The header of WATERLINE website and the content of drop-down menu

2.2 Footer

Figure 2 shows the footer of WATERLINE website, it clearly explains the project is funded by the European Commission’s Horizon Europe programme.

Figure 2 The footer of WATERLINE website

2.3 Project introduction

Figure 3 shows the landing page of WATERLINE highlights the key components, i.e. aim, methodology, and work packages of the project. Users may follow the associated links to find more details, which are shown in Figures 4-6.

About WATERLINE

Figure 3 The landing page of WATERLINE website

Aim

WATERLINE

WATERLINE aims to create a European Digital Water Higher Education Institution (HEI) Alliance, based on the quadruple helix model of innovation, leading to the development of the Alliance's research, educational and entrepreneurship capacities. This shall leverage the individual, institutional and regional resources required for a transformative structural and sustainable learning and innovation environment.

To achieve this, WATERLINE has five specific objectives:

Objective 1

Objective 2

Objective 3

Objective 4

Objective 5

Figure 4 The aim and objectives of WATERLINE

Methodology

WATERLINE methodology consists of four phases that involve: (i) mapping; (ii) engaging and co-designing; (iii) implementing, and (iv) positioning and building excellence.

PHASE 1: MAPPING. The mapping Phase sets the basis for the realisation of all the pillars of WATERLINE and will provide direct input to its subsequent phases. Currently, partner HEIs have different requirements, such as curricula requirements, and hold different types of expertise.

PHASE 2 ENGAGING and CO-DESIGNING. In line with and building on the priorities set in Phase 1, the second phase will co-design a number of frameworks/plans to implement the digital water HEI alliance.

PHASE 3 IMPLEMENTING. The actions co-designed in Phase 2 will be transformed and implemented in Phase 3.

Three distinct Learning Environments (LEs) will be co-created in WATERLINE:

- (1) The Emulated LE (ELE): The HEIs already have existent emulation infrastructures that replicate the real environment in a controlled, scaled-down manner, within a laboratory or workshop environment. This physical test, emulation and research setup allow learners to carry out the more complex skilling exercises in a safe and guided manner, that will precede the skilling in an assisted LE.
- (2) The Assisted Reality LE (ARLE): This LE is complementary and in enhancement to the ELE, and will extend learning within a physical training environment that is as close as possible to the real water environment. The learning would be enhanced through assisted reality, that is, technology-enabled tools or methods that enhance and add insights, technical information and guidance to the learner.
- (3) The Virtual LE (ViLE): This LE complements and replicates ELE and ARLE, allowing learners to study the same water topics within a virtual environment, entirely remotely. The inclusion of ViLE shall be supported by a platform of virtual reality tools and methodologies that the involved HEIs shall commonly deploy. This shall enable advancement of academic and researcher capacities to include that of operating and designing within virtual environments.

Figure 5 The methodology of WATERLINE

Work Packages

WP1 WP2 WP3 WP4 WP5 WP6

WP1 Coordination and management (MCAST)

The overall objective of WP1 is to coordinate the project activities and the work of partners involved to ensure the proper time management and implementation of activities and the financial and administrative management of the project for the timely delivery of quality results. The specific objectives of WP1 are to:

- O1.1 Provide efficient and effective management of the project, management of the WPs and coordination among participants.
- O1.2 Exchange of information with the project team and a communication channel for the EC.

Task 1.1 Overall project management (MCAST)

Task 1.2 Management of the project consortium and bodies (MCAST)

Task 1.3 Quality Assurance (MCAST)

Figure 6 The work package of WATERLINE

2.4 Project partners

Figure 7 shows the webpage that explains the geographic distribution of WATERLINE partners and the coordinator. Figure 8 is the webpage for introducing WATERLINE consortium members and associated partners, with the logo and website link of each partner.

Figure 7 Consortium webpage showing the geographic distribution of WATERLINE partners and the project coordinator

Consortium members

Mendel University in Brno (MENDELU)

University of Niš (UNI)

Dokuz Eylül University (DEU-DESUM)

Università degli Studi Mediterranea di Reggio Calabria (UNIRC)

Norwegian University of Life Sciences (NMBU)

Turku University of Applied Sciences (TUAS)

University of Exeter (UNEXE)

Sustainable Innovation Technology Services (SITES)

H2O People (H2O People)

Accreditation Council for Entrepreneurial and Engaged Universities (ACEEU)

Associated Partners

Water Services Corporation (WSC)

Energy and Water Agency (EWA)

FULL SCALE DYNAMICS LTD

Full Scale Dynamics (FSD)

CREA Hydro & Energy (CREA)

Figure 8 Consortium members and associated partners information page

2.5 Project News & Events

Figure 9 shows the latest news from the WATERLINE consortium. It will also include upcoming project events and dissemination activities, as well as the newsletter. Users can subscribe to the WATERLINE Newsletter, as shown in Figure 10, such that they will automatic receive notification when a Newsletter is released.

News & Events

Waterline kick-off meeting

 Events

DATE 06-07 December 6, 2022 Venue: MCAST

[READ MORE...](#)

**INTRODUCING "WATERLINE"
2022: OUR FIRST HORIZON
PROJECT**

 News

H2O-People is a proud partner of Waterline, a HORIZON-WIDERA-2021 project, which kickoff online in October. "Waterline" is an acronym for Transforming Advanced Water Skilling through the Creation of a Network of Extended-Reality Water Emulative Centres.

[READ MORE...](#)

Centre for Water Systems secures funding boost for pivotal research and education projects

 News

Two pivotal new projects, led by experts from the University of Exeter and designed to bolster research and education within the water sector, have secured a significant funding boost. The new projects, led by world-leading researchers from Exeter's The Centre for Water Systems (CWS), have secured £450,000 from Horizon Europe, the EU's key funding programme for research and innovation into some of the world's greatest challenges.

[READ MORE...](#)

Figure 9 WATERLINE News & Event webpage

Newsletter subscription

Please use the following for to subscribe WATERLINE Newsletter

[SUBSCRIBE](#)

Figure 10 WATERLINE Newsletter subscription form

2.6 Project outcomes

Figure 11 shows the Deliverables download page of the projection outcomes. All published materials including reports, journal and conference papers, presentation slides, documents, codes, videos etc. will be shared via corresponding subsections within the page.

The screenshot shows the WATERLINE website's Deliverables page. The header includes the WATERLINE logo, navigation links (Home, News & Events, Outcomes, Related projects, Contact), and social media icons (Twitter, LinkedIn, Facebook). The main content area is titled "Deliverables" and lists various project deliverables organized into groups:

- D1.1 Quality assurance plan
- D1.2 Data Management Plan
- D1.3 EC financial and technical reporting
- D1.4 Internal Progress reports
- D2.1 WATERLINE governance framework
- D2.2 WATERLINE R&I capacity building plan
- D3.1 Digital Water Curriculum component
- D3.2 Compendium of capacity building output
- D3.3 Group project business pitching report
- D4.1 WATERLINE website
- D4.2 Technical and user documentation for the three learning environments
- D4.3 Report on feedback provided during the pilot implementation
- D5.1 Report "R&I Funding Landscape: opportunities for WATERLINE"
- D5.2 Policy exploitation guideline recommendations
- D6.1 Communication Strategic Plan
- D6.2 Plan for Dissemination and Exploitation of the Results
- D6.3 Clustering Plan
- D6.4 Mid-term report on C&D activities
- D6.5 Final report on C&D activities

The footer contains the European Union logo, the text "WATERLINE project receives funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ACCESS-05 under grant agreement No 101071306.", and a "Back to top" link with an upward arrow.

Figure 11 WATERLINE Deliverables list page

2.7 Related projects

Figure 12 shows the related projects and their weblinks that are under the same List of related projects in the HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ACCESS-05. This will establish the connections with those projects.

The screenshot shows the WATERLINE website's 'Related projects' page. The page has a dark blue header with the WATERLINE logo and navigation links: Home, News & Events, Outcomes, Related projects, and Contact. Social media icons for Twitter, LinkedIn, and Facebook are also present. The main content area is white and features a section titled 'Related projects' with a list of project names and their descriptions:

AeroSTREAM	Strengthening Research and Innovation Excellence in Autonomous Aerial Systems
BETTER Life	Bringing Excellence to Transformative Socially Engaged Research in Life Sciences through Integrated Digital Centers
BI4E	BOOSTING INGENIUM FOR EXCELLENCE
E3UDRES2 Ent-r-e-novators	E3UDRES2 Ent-r-e-novators: Cooperating for excellence and impact in research and innovation
Edu4ClimAte	European Higher Education Institutions Network for Climate and Atmospheric Sciences
EXPER	Excellent peripheries for a strong European Research Area
InCITIES	Trailblazing Inclusive, Sustainable and Resilient Cities
Sustainable Horizons	European Universities designing the horizons of sustainability

At the bottom of the page, there is a dark blue footer containing the European Union logo, the text 'WATERLINE project receives funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ACCESS-05 under grant agreement No 101071306.', and a 'Back to top' link with an upward arrow icon.

Figure 12 List of related projects in the HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ACCESS-05 call

2.8 Contact

Figure 13 display the contact information of the WATERLINE project, allowing visitors to contact with the project team.

Contact

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[Next >](#)

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Figure 13 WATERLINE contact information

2.9 Visitor statistics

Google Analytics has been adopted to is applied to record the numbers of page visits. Figure 14 shows the anonymous statistic information of page visits from Google Analytics. The application will enable continuous monitoring of KPI (visits), understanding the geographical distribution of visitors, and the popular topics and pages on the website.

Figure 14 Anonymous WATERLINE webpage visitor statistic information in Google Analytics

Project Partners

